

“By His Wounds We Are Healed:” Meditation on the Five Wounds of Jesus

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“⁴Surely he took up our pain
and bore our suffering,
yet we considered him punished by God,
stricken by him, and afflicted.

⁵ But he was pierced for our transgressions,
he was crushed for our iniquities;
the punishment that brought us peace was on him,
and by his wounds we are healed.” (Is.53:4-5 NIV)

Centuries before the crucifixion of Jesus prophet Isaiah prophesied the barbaric event of the Crucified, the suffering Servant of Yahweh. Early Christians saw its literal happening on calvary a. Innocent Servant of God suffered the wages of sin in his body for the redemption of humanity. Prophet Isaiah prophesied that ‘by his wounds we will be healed’.

Due to COVID 19 the whole humanity is going through suffering in body, mind and spirit. Let’s approach the crucified who is still hung on Calvary all over the world so as to receive healing touch from his wounds. In our imagination lets travel back in time to Calvary where the event took place. With much reverence we shall take up this journey. In our heart let our prayer be from the hymn Stabat Mater “Holy Mother pierce me through/In my heart each wound renew/of my savior crucified.”

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As I arrive at Calvary, I see already the body of Jesus is laid in the hands of Mother Mary. There let me stand close to his body gazing at each wound, clotted blood, broken flesh, gaping wounds pierced by the nails.

“Holy Mother pierce me through/In my heart each wound renew/of my savior crucified.” Stabat Mater

The Right Hand

Let me look at the wound of the **right hand** of Jesus pierced by the nail. Gaping wound, flesh torn apart. I hold the right hand of Jesus in my hand and kiss the wound with reverence and devotion. I recall to mind what these hands have done for humanity. These hands touched the lepers, and were healed. These hands touch the eyes of the visually impaired, speech impaired, hearing impaired and they were made whole. These hands distributed food to the hungry, washed the feet of his disciples, broke the bread and gave the wine poured out for the salvation of the humanity and asked his disciples to do the same. In this innocent and loving hand pierced by the nail, into that wound I place all those who are suffering from COVID 19 and I pray that they all be healed.

The Left Hand

Then I proceed to the **left hand of Jesus**. With reverence and devotion I kiss that wound. I recall to my mind the works these hands have done. These hands lifted Talitha who was dead, the young man of Nain was given life. These hands blessed the water into wine and saved the family from embarrassment. These hands touched the broken ear of the soldier Malchus and he was healed. These hands lifted Peter who was drowning in the sea. These hands prepared breakfast to his disciples on the bank of the lake Tiberias. Into this hand pierced by the nail I place all the bereaved members of the family who have lost their loved ones due to the COVID 19. I pray that the Lord may console and strengthen them.

The Right Foot

Now I move to the feet of Jesus. I hold **the right foot of Jesus** in my hand. With reverence and devotion I kiss that wound. As I gaze at that wound I recall to my mind what these feet have done for humanity. He walked and walked to the towns and villages of Palestine. As he travelled he preached about the Kingdom of God. Preached the good news to the poor and the broken hearted. He went in search of sinners. He walked on

the sea shore and invited young to follow him so as to continue His mission. He walked into the house of Peter and healed his mother in law. He went to the house of Simon the Pharisee and taught him about love and mercy. He went to the house of Zacchaeus inviting him to experience the joy of salvation. He walked to the temple and to the synagogue preaching and healing the sick. At his foot I bring all the health workers, doctors and people of good will who are engaged in serving those affected by Corona virus. I pray that they all be protected from. Their families be blessed with many graces.

The Left Foot

Now hold the **left foot of Jesus** in my hand. I kiss the wound with reverence and devotion. I recall to my mind what these feet have done. He walked his way to Jerusalem to face his HOUR destined by his Father. He walked his way to the garden of Gethsemane to pray so as to draw strength from His Father. He walked his way to Calvary carrying His cross. There he was nailed to the cross and hung on the cross till he breathed his

last. After the resurrection he walked to the places where his disciples were huddled together out of fear of the Jews. He brought them joy, peace and courage. He walked with the two disciples on the way to Emmaus revealing them to the meaning of the Scriptures about himself. To this feet now I bring all the political and ecclesial, religious leaders of the world. I pray that the Lord may strengthen them so that they will be enabled to deal with this crisis affecting the whole humanity.

The Pierced Side of Jesus

Now I stand close to the **pierced side of Jesus**. Soldiers wanted to confirm the death of Jesus. So one of them with a lance pierced his side and water and blood flowed. As I gaze at the pierced heart of Jesus, I recall to my mind how he was moved to compassion when he saw the crowds who were like sheep without shepherd. He asked his disciples to pray to the Father so that He will send more labourers to carry on the mission. He wept at the tomb of Lazar. He wept gazing at the city of Jerusalem which was not recognizing its time of salvation.

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Conclusion

After the resurrection he was moved with compassion to meet his frightened disciples who had lost all their hope. To this pierced side of Jesus, I bring all those persons who have lost their hope and feel imprisoned at home not knowing when all this will be over. Those poor persons, migrant labourers, unemployed, lonely, sick, living on the pavements, in the slums, who are hungry and thirsty so that they all be taken care by the generous people of good will.

I close this prayer thanking the Lord for his healing touches and say the prayer which the Lord has taught us “Our Father who art in heaven.....”

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To this pierced side of Jesus, I bring all those persons who have lost their hope and feel imprisoned at home not knowing when all this will be over. Those poor persons, migrant labourers, unemployed, lonely, sick, living on the pavements, in the slums, who are hungry and thirsty so that they all be taken care by the generous people of good will.